

The Effect of Leaders' Behavioral Selection Assessments on Non-For-Profit Organization's Performance in Saudi Arabia

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Abstract:

This study examines the impact of leaders' Behavioral Selection Assessments (BSA) on the performance of Non-Profit Organizations (NPOs) in Saudi Arabia. Amid the rapid growth of the Saudi non-profit sector under Vision 2030, organizations face increasing pressure to recruit qualified leaders. While functional selection assessments (FSA) remain widely used, behavioral assessments may offer stronger predictive validity for leadership effectiveness. This research develops and empirically tests a conceptual framework linking BSA, FSA, pressure to hire, and government support variables to NPO performance. Using a quantitative research design, data were collected from senior leaders and HR managers in Saudi NPOs. Regression analysis was conducted to test the proposed hypotheses. Findings indicate that behavioral selection assessments significantly predict organizational performance, while excessive pressure to hire negatively affects performance. Government financial support and regulatory frameworks demonstrate moderating effects. The study contributes to leadership selection literature and offers practical implications for HR governance in the non-profit sector.

Keywords: Behavioral Selection, Assessments, Leadership, Non-Profit Organizational Performanc, Saudi Arabian Non-Profit Sector

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 History of Non-for-profit sector in Saudi Arabia:

Prior to the 20th century, the NPS informal activities started to serve the less fortunate, through a vital role played by philanthropy and religious institutions to serve the community and supporting social welfare. These activities started to be organized after launching the ministry of Labor and Social affairs in 1380 H, 1961 (Ministry of Economy & Planning, 2023). It had Steady growing during the 20th century but started to be diversified to include educational organizations, charitable foundations and social institutes and the government started to boost its growing by providing tax exemptions initiatives and supporting philanthropic interventions. 2016 was the most important year passed by the NPS as it was the publication year for the NPS law, that organized most of the aspects that govern the sector and started to deal with it as a third sector beside the private sector and the government sector (International Center for Not-for-Profit Law, 2017) while the number of the non-for-profit organizations before 2015 was 1500 organization, a dramatic growth happen through the past eight years the NPS has been doubled and reached 3361 NPO (Council of Economic and Development Affairs, 2023), which classified a significance growth in order to achieve the target contribution in the national GDP 5% according to Saudi Arabia 2030 vision (Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, 2016).

This dramatic growth put high-pressure on all the support functions working in the space around the NPS, which can be classified into three parties. First the NPS represented in this

study by its human resources working force, or who are potentially to be attracted by the same sector. Second is the government, which puts great efforts to support the NPS with regulations, financial support, and facilities, and even establishing subsidiary foundations to give direct hand to support NGOs and NPOs. The third party is the private sector, which started to calculate its contribution in the community obligated by the community pressure, government facilities given to the private sector organizations that support the NPS and by social community pressure. Private sector organizations started to establish corporate social responsibility departments to support the community and NPS. This momentum reached the private sector employees who started to give their pro-bono, which is professional volunteer hours in their specialty in the NGOs and NPOs maybe daily monthly or yearly. On the other hand, the government started to bless and encourage private sector employees to record their volunteer hours with the NPS on the governmental portal (Absher) that may be part of their recognition or privileges given to people who invested some hours in serving the community and record the hours on the portal. The cooperation of these three parties, the government, the private sector, and the NPS we can call it the developmental triangle.

1.2 Problem Definition:

NPOs' community services are now in a very high demand due to the successive crises facing the world, either the first world or the developing countries. There is lack of NPOs leaders (Apostu, 2013) that obligate the NPOs to be more permissive and lenient to support the inflow of leaders. There is a challenge that according to 2030 vision for the kingdom non-for-profit sector should increase and contribute in the national GDP from 1% to be 5%, which means it should grow steadily by around 35% every year depending on 2016 data as baseline (KSA's national source for government services and information, 2023). Also, the recruitment challenges in NPS according to the general authority of statistics is 19.33% from the surveyed challenges facing it (statistics, 2018) that means clearly the supply is dramatically lower than demand and many cooperated interventions should be boosted to reach an acceptable balance. Driven by their accelerated services demand, NPOs used to hire many leaders sometimes compromising their selection value-based standards to satisfy the high demand and the narrow supply of leaders who can successfully carry out the NPOs' objectives (Batti, 2014). Convincing with the ordinary practices like technical selection attempts for example accounting test for accountant, legal test for legal affairs candidate, labor low testing for HR candidates led to an acceptable injected candidates working in the NPO without behavioral testing or assessment, which consequently at many situations lead to attitude firing, minor and major misconduct and disengaged employees or volunteers due to the behavioral problems. Added more complexity to the problem, that the newly injected leaders -who have bad or unwanted behaviors- are qualified technically, as they passed each technical or functional exams!! So, it will be very hard to management or HR to elaborate why this newly hired -technically qualified- leader should be fired due to the difficulty of evaluating tangibly the unwanted behaviors of the guy, or the difficulty of proving how these bad behaviors are affecting work or the organizational final records.

According to John Maxwell, organizations hire thousands of MBA holders, top technically classified degrees and promoting them very quickly due to what they study, what they owned from multiple degrees not on their top-rated behaviors. Knowledge and intelligence are nothing in regards of the persons' effectiveness unless he could mix them with imagination and get an effective personality that created the best intercorrelation between these technicalities and behaviors and interpersonal skills. Taking into consideration that more than

50% of leaders of the big 500 fortunes got C and below in their colleges!!, 65% of all united states senators came from the lower split of their schools!! (Maxwell, 2011, pp. 146-147)

1.3 Significance of the study:

As the world still tottering from the pandemic period it followed by Russia and Ukraine war, all that lead to a world economic growth slowing down, USA Europe and China faces and expected to face increasing unforecasted inflation rates. That will put pressure on the first world countries and put enormous pressure on the developed countries (Gourinchas, 2022). Here comes the crucial role of the NPS which relieves the high pressure on the government shoulders without materialistic return on investment requested like the private sector practices. As there are growing need to the NPS role it came the need to develop this sector, assess its capacity and capabilities to carry this hard responsibility that the governments can't carry itself with all this chain of uncontrolled worldwide crises and economical challenges.

Before the beginning of that chain -before the pandemic- NPS was doing its work in a moderate demanding environment, services delivered, community services where at the acceptable levels without any pressures. That reflected on the selection of this sectors leaders' criteria. Unlike the private sectors harsh selection tools, the NPS didn't face that heat before the pandemic. All previous selected leaders' criteria have been examined during the pandemic and proved that there is a high demand of boosting professional selection criteria for NP leaders to enhance the NPOs capacity which consequently obligated leaders to serve either wide range from the community or providing more professional, impactful, and In-need services for the same range.

1.4 Research questions:

•Major Question

What are the variables that affecting the NPOs' performance.

•Minor Questions

1. What is the impact of the **Behavioural selection assessments** for leaders in NPOs' performance?

Claim: there are a direct positive strong relation between **Leaders' BSA** and the the NPOs' performance.

2. What is the impact of the Functional selection assessments for leaders in NPOs' performance?

Claim: there are a direct positive strong relation between **leaders' FSA** and the the NPOs' performance.

3. What is the impact of the pressure to hire on the NPOs performance?

Claim: there are a direct negative relation between the pressure to hire and the NPOs' performance.

4. Does the Government financial hiring support affect the NPOs performance?

Claim: The Government financial hiring support directly affect the 3 dependent variables

5. Do the government regulations affect the NPOs' performance?

Claim: The Government regulations directly affect the 3 dependent variables

1.5 Variables & Variables' Identification:

-Dependent variable:

NPOs Performance. The ability of the NPO to achieve its goals financially and non-financially. Its financial sustainability, programs' impact and its correlation with the organization's mission did it worked directly to achieve the organization mission? or it deviated

while the implementation phase? Also, the management ability to attract, engage and retain talents to carry out the succession responsibility faced by external and internal influences.

- Independent Variables:

1. Behavioral selection assessments:

It is meant by behavioral selection tools, all the mental and psychological assessments conducted to assure HOW the leader is going to behave in a certain way in the future while managing his role and across multiple and fluctuated circumstances.

A strong positive relation exists between the **Behavioral Selection Assessments** and the dependent variable, when the BSA increases the NPO performance increase.

2. Functional Selection Assessments:

It is meant by functional selection tools, all the technical assessments conducted to assure the leaders knowledge and functional experience will benefit the mission of the NPO. It is directly related to the leader's academic background, learning experience and WHAT he achieved from previous functional targets or outcomes.

A strong positive relation exists between the **Functional Selection Assessments** and the dependent variable when the FSA increases the NPO performance increase.

3. Pressure to hire:

As NPOs numbers raised dramatically from 1500 to 3361 (Council of Economic and Development Affairs, 2023) so there where a very high pressure laying on the NPOs to hire senior management rapidly through its scarcity. This direct and indirect pressure is from donors, communities and even the government.

A negative relation exists between the pressure to hire and the dependent variable, when the pressure to hire increase the NPO performance decrease

- Moderating Variables:

4. Government financial support: financial support given by the government to NPOs to hire the major positions, it has a direct both positive and negative impact on NPOs performance.

5. Government NPS regulations: the government rules and regulations that govern the NPS. It has a direct both positive and negative impact on NPOs' performance.

1.6 Hypotheses:

H1: The Behavioral selection assessments has positive influence on the NPO performance.

H2: The Functional selection assessment has positive influence on the NPO performance.

H3: The pressure to hire has negative influence on the NPO performance.

H4: Government financial support has a direct both positive and negative impact on NPOs performance.

H5: Government non-for-profit sectors' regulations has a direct both positive and negative impact on NPOs performance.

Conceptual schematic framework

2. LITERATURE REVIEW:

2.1 Dependent Variable:

In our study we found many literatures highlighted the great influence of the leader's performance on the NPOs performance. As there is direct correlation between the NPO effectiveness and the leaders' competencies and capabilities in enabling the NPO to achieve greater social impact and carrying its ultimate role in serving the community, it is more broader than outputs, goal achievements and well written key performance indicators and more deeper than gaining some community awards or attaining a quality certificate or healthy internal environment recognition, we can summarize this effectiveness in the following categories:

Organization Mission: How the leader transformed the NPO mission into common language and specific milestones and measurable KPIs, then progress is being assessed and reported to stakeholders. According to (Arbogust, 2020) leaders may be a main reason of the NPO mission drifting, which means that the NPO accepted programs that are not its core or main speciality, that leads over time to fade out from the main mission and reason of existence of the NPO. So, there is a crucial role should be played by NPO leaders to act as guardian to its mission and try to feed it with impactful interventions to serve the community and not go to the easy way of accepting donations or Ceed funding that obligate them to accept the doner interest which may be far from the NPO mission. Leaders does not act only as guardians of the mission, but they are the creators too. The NPO mission requires wide spectrum of strategic thinking, awareness of the community needs, readiness to think differently to satisfy the community requirements with creative and innovative solutions. All these interventions, although they appear as an operational part but the main driver of them comes from a very well-designed mission so it's not just a statement. It is an organic part influenced by the community and re-influencing the community again in a continuous service and feedback circle.

Stakeholders' relationship management: NPO leader has multiple stakeholders need to be wisely managed or managing their expectation to the good of the NPO starting from the board passing by the regulating entities, NPO employees, doners and the community. The better the relationships are the more success in achieving its tangible and intangible targets and impact (Mohammed Aboramadan, 2021). It's not easy to maintain balanced and healthy relations with

all these parties as some of them are contradicting in their interests from other stakeholders, like if a NPO working in distributing some governmental funds upon other eligible NPOs and how to manage this relation. Also handling the NPO board to report influential projects while being a cost-effective leader in the same report, finally managing engaging interventions to motivate the NPO employees or attract others to work there while managing a balanced financial expense.

All these are burdens on the leaders' shoulders and should manage wisely. It doesn't mean by the stockholder's relationship management that it is done by the person on the top of the NPO this responsibility relying on all the NPO leaders' shoulders each of them has his own role and ready to expand his role vertically or horizontally for the benefit of the NPO. Each leader is ready to cover his colleague in order not to leave any stakeholder relationship management gap, the transparency, the governance practices, the financial awareness reports, subordinates performance records, coaching and mentorship for the entire teams, motivating and engaging the NPO employees studying the current status of the community and the economy, and anticipating the changes may come in the shape of opportunities or even threats, all these activities should be played cleverly by the NPO leaders, and each leader has to have his own contribution in all these aspects that are not related to his specialization, but it's related to his leadership role should be played across the NPO.

Financial Management and financial sustainability: Assess how leaders are managing the NPO financial resources and better allocating them to achieve its mission, How leaders effectively working on budgeting, diversifying financial sourcing or fundraising and reaching the financial sustainability of the NPO which consequently protecting it from the normal economical fluctuations (Sehrish Ilyas, 2020). According to (Denisa Gajdová, 2018) 61% of the financial income of the NPOs comes from private financial sourcing. This percentage is threatening the NPOs, and leaders always are working to increase the financial independency rather than relying on private financial sourcing like donations and private sectors contribution which is fluctuated and always affected by the economic status. Although it is crucial to keep good continues streams of private financial sources but diversifying financial sources, efficiently managing costs, and increasing the financial independency became and emerging needs. Also, it assesses the leader's mindset in sustaining the NPO interventions and impact, how he assures the NPO continuity and risk management, how he is anticipating the future and prepare his plans to deal with its opportunities and threats. The current economy fluctuation is forcing NPO leaders to prepare solutions and financially sustainable plans to prepare their NPOs to be stand-alone without much more dependence on external donors, having its own projects and profitable interventions that serving the community, and at the same time get a return on investment that enables the NPO to hire more qualified calibres and make good expansion in its services and may do some research and development to enhance their products or services delivered. This will not keep the NPO away from the NPS, but it is supporting the NPO to survive in such fluctuated economy.

Impact analysis Micro level and Macro level: Assesses the NPO programs outcomes and the impact of its interventions on the targeted beneficiaries, also it evaluates the consistency between the programs and the NPO mission. unlike the for-profit organizations the setting goals in the NPO are more hard and difficult to be completely measured, here comes the role of monitoring and evaluation which make the most benefit from data generations on the scale of projects and programs guarantee that what is being achieved actually is completely compatible with the real purpose of the program impact plan and the organization mission

consequently (Nalianya Japheth Micah, 2017). On the Macro level it assesses the leaders' capabilities to scale-up the interventions of the NPO that achieves impactful success to influence segment of the community or even the legalization that governs the similar NPOs. this happened through the professional data and knowledge management regarding the NPOs successful programs and its continuous replication till the extension that formulates a decision support tool to the NPS key players, they use these data to prove that certain change should take place or specific transformation should occur. This proves then the leader's ability to enable the NPO to – positively- influence the community or a large segment of it.

Impartiality and transparency: Assesses the ability of the leaders to transparently report the NPO interventions' outcomes and the internal achievements and how they introduce any drops or challenges without making up! The most important need for transparency is the financial reports, not only the traditional ones like financial statements but more deeper analysis that enable the donors or the strategic ones to track their funds across the implemented programs as main donors most likely trying to drive the programs to their donation interests, they firstly choose the NPOs or NGOs that translates their mission and values, then go deeper to influence the program or program flagship and even the beneficiaries. According to a study 61% of doners mentioned the importance of the financial report's transparency, reliability 60 and being easy to understand 47% (Carolyn J. Cordery, 2017).

NPO resilience and innovation: Assesses how the NPO leaders capable to lean to the changing circumstances and how they can foster innovation in developing new and unique interventions differentiating its impact from the traditional ones or rescuing the NPO from unexpected setbacks. The disruption is the main organizations enemy, and leaders should be always alerted to boost their maximum innovation and resilience to stand in the upfront line and not be disrupted, we saw in the Covid-19 many NPOs closed and many of them suffered from cash deficit. Digital transformation, innovated programs and interventions, new cost-effective ways of implementing community programs and many other examples of the organization resilience and innovation (Witmer, 2016). As a result of this needed NPO resilience, we noticed one of the Consulting NPOs and during the COVID-19 pandemic it was going to make a major layoff for near to 35% of the workforce, and after some research and study of the current community need at that time they found many opportunities can be done for the community with a good or acceptable ROI, but it need to make major restructuring for the human resource departments in the entire NPO. They took the hard decision and kept all its employees and made this harsh restructuring. It challenged its departmentalization and opened all the borders between all the NPO employees and reconnected them in small groups. Each group can function all the NPO functions separate from the other group, so each group has sales role, fundraising role, innovation role, program management role, project management role, and even secretary and logistics role. Each group worked on certain opportunities, approaching certain beneficiaries got some projects, worked on the implementation, and got a sufficient ROI that sustained the NPO at those very hard times, this restructuring called holacracy structure. This resilient action taken by the NPO saved it from laying of its good human resources and help the organization not only to survive, but to achieve the highest revenues they have ever achieved, although it was in the COVID-19 period, this is the organizational resilience.

Employees and volunteers' engagement and development: Assesses how the leader is looking at his human resources and how he is dealing with in terms of development and engagement. How he is investing in them and treated the talents as his main capital same

important like the NPO financial one. NPOs leaders are more likely to have close relations with their employees, as achieving objectives and clear goals not like the for-profit organization it needs more human relations to be near to the community projects. This requires from the leaders to be more towards the coaching style at work. It doesn't mean to be lenient or lacking control he still has the charted course and his subordinate adherence to rules and regulations, but the engagement activities, human relations and individual management must be there while managing their employees in the NPO environment. Employee is crucial to NPO sustainability so employee commitment towards goals fulfilment and his organizational citizenship are two main results of engagement practices (Kunle Akingbola, 2019).

Employee engagement is not a one-time activity it is a continuous activities with a cyclic feedback process, starting from assessing the employees needs exploring what engage them and encouraging them to do the extra mile for the benefit of the NPO and the community consequently, it may need to conduct some internal surveys to let the employees express their needs openly and anonymously, then analysing these survey outputs and translate their output into engagement plans after classifying them into tangible and intangible engagement interventions. This should be one of the highest priorities for the internal human resource team, and this engagement activities should not be exclusive on the full-time employees, but also should cover for certain acceptable extend the volunteers working with the NPO. The interventions may differ between them, but they should not be forgotten, keeping the employees engaged in this high competition and leaders' attraction between NPO's and other NPOs, or NPOs and the private sector, or even the government is crucial, to retain the NPO current leaders and pillars without facing any leaders gap or deficiency in the NPO performance because of high leadership turnover percentages.

Attraction and retention: Assesses leaders' capabilities to make their NPO attractive and appealing to high performers and what is the internal motivation and engagement system sponsored by these leaders to retain their skilful staff. tangible and non-tangible attractions and retention should be mixed in the NPOs like the power of the shared values that boost a good meaning that the employee may compromise his salary could be paid in a for-profit organization to work in the NPO, and tangible benefits like family incentives would also be a powerful attraction and retention technique to raise these two percentages. Also opening the space for employees' performance improvement and continuous acknowledgement that their efforts lead to their organization success let them feel with fulfilment and motivates them to put more effort as they see its tangible impact and consequently increase employee's retention (Lise Anne Slatten, 2021).

Designing attractive employment packages is not wasting for the NPO money some leaders wrongly think that having an attractive packages is not recommended as they are not a private organizations while on the other side, other leaders think that they should design creative employment packages to attract professional practitioners from the private sector that is already headhunting leaders from them with its appealing packages and benefits, it is not mandatory that the attractive package should contain a market niche payment but also it should contain a wise and innovative mixture of monetary and non-monetary benefits taking into consideration that the type of people looking to work in the NPO values the mission and community servicing field so they have unspoken donation readiness of their time although the NPO will not heavily depending on that, but it should be considered while designing the attractive package for the full-time employees working with the NPO. We can say that attraction leads to retention and retention leads to attraction as retaining good leaders can

attract other good leaders and attracting good leaders may retain the current professional leaders, so it is a very good cycle of leaders' generation and leaders' retention.

All these categories are synchronized with each other to proof or achieve the NPO effectiveness these categories, are influenced externally by the external uncontrolled influences like regulations, government governance obligations, economical influences, and political issues but also there are the controllable aspects which leaders use to achieve the NPO ultimate objectives and fulfil its mission. Coming in the centre of this controllable enablers, the human capital, which is also acting as the most important and crucial enabler for the NPO to reach its ultimate community services and quality. Keeping that in mind and dealing with the human capital as the main asset and the most important mandatory retained one is the basis of our study specifically the selection of this human capital on a scientific and reliable basis.

Independent Variable, Behavioral selection assessments:

The usage of knowledge and technical side of the person in the selection phase is not sufficient, if we took example coping with change, it may not lead as to predict his performance from his functional know how or technical side In his experience unless his adaptability, and changeability traits are tested to proof that within the selection process (Paul R. SACKETT, 2008). Behavioral selection is not an assessment tool, it's an assessment type consists of many tools like behavioral interview (BI) or competency-based interview (CBI), assessment center (AC), Emotional intelligence questionnaire EQ and Occupational Personality Questionnaire (OPQ). All these tools are used selectively by the recruiters to assess the applicant leaders' behaviors and anticipate his future behaviors in his coming new role. According to Robert McCrae and Paul Costa, personality have five dimensions Openness, Conscientiousness, agreeableness, neuroticism, and Extraversion. We found great influence of these personality traits and job performance. We could predict the employee performance on his job if we managed to reach valid and reliable assessment on him based on the big five factors personality model (Mario Lado, 2017)

Any job like a coin with two faces, explicit and implicit faces, the explicit is (specific job experience & job knowledge) and the implicit (traits, personality attribute), these two faced should be examined and assessed in order to come up with the best hiring decision which will affects the NPO performance and success (Filip LIEVENS, 2016) the easy way is to just assessing the technical (explicit) job specification as it has clear and almost measurable criteria, while the difficult part is to assess the senior leaders personality attributes in order to see how he is going to contribute with his competencies in the NPO success

2.2 Independent Variable, Functional Selection Assessments:

Functional selection is depending on the employees technical or specialized experience, cognitive ability and job role knowledge to select certain candidate (Murray R. Barrick, 2019), it is crucial in employee's selection and more widely used by recruiters cause it is more easier to judge the applicant and reach hire/not hire decision. It was typically made by the superior one (the candidate future boss) or made by third party to give technical judgement. As any job needs specialist to carry out its responsibilities like accounting job, we need the candidate to be assessed in accounting field to be sure that he can fulfill this job requirements and will not face any functional difficulties while performing his role. This assessment part also considered a key intervention in the NPO success in achieving its goals. This type of assessment was the man type before the rising of the industrial psychology and human studies which assured that there is a more or similar personality aspect should be tested before nominating the person for a certain position beside the functional aspects and technical experience.

2.3 Independent Variable, Pressure to hire:

After the recent economical fluctuations during the period between 2020 and 2023, it seems that the unemployment raised rates will solve any hiring problem. With all respect to other skilled workers who have been downsized due to the organizations inability to afford their monthly packages financially, on the other side many organizations downsized human resources who are not in the talent pool and market seems to be filled with unemployed but unskilled workers according to the organizational demographical ranked downsizing (Baharudin D, 2021). That put more pressure on organizations to hire or even headhunt more qualified candidates from other organizations, the more pressure laid on the organizations the more recruiting standards are broken by them till the extension they started making poaching and lateral hiring (Joseph Amankwah-Amoah, 2015) many of the market salaries' schemes and working conditions are overpassed in order to win in the race, it's like boiling water under a steady surface, the steady quite surface is the rising of unemployed rates and the boiling water under it is the competition to hunt the talents or qualified employees. Although it may be healthy and lead the candidates sharpening their saws but on the other organizational side it may lead the NPO to bypass many hiring standards and conditions just to fill the gap (Cappelli, 1995).

2.4 Moderate Variable, Government financial support:

Saudi government attempts to facilitate the hiring process financially, as the newly established NGO or NPO needs some establishment funds or recruitment funds as that portion of money the founders cannot afford due to the raising establishment expenses. Here came a volunteer initiative from the Saudi government and ministry of human resources and social development represented in many subsidiary foundations playing key role in supporting NPOs, like housing development that spent over 1 billion in the housing development NGOs support as establishments funds, recruitment funds and consequently withing five years offered houses for needy Saudi families (agency, 2023). This continues support encourages NPOs to hire the needed positions without financial burden but at the same time it has no audit control on the chosen candidates and may lead to hire the easy way without comprehensive recruitment activities to enhance the selection phase.

2.5 Moderate Variable, Government regulations:

Saudi government regulations became easier for establishment associations and NGOs till the extension that number of NGOs before 2015 was 1500 and withing the last 7 years only this number has been more than doubled to reach 3340 NGO (King Khalid Foundation, 2023). It also has both edges; one is the hiring expansion of the NPOs and being a noticeable player started to attract candidates and leader's ant that obligated the NPOs to qualify its recruitment practices and the second edge that the expansion is too rapid that it may exceeds their capacity to reach the recruitment and selection practices enhancements.

3. METHODOLOGY

This study adopts a quantitative cross-sectional design. Data were collected using a structured questionnaire distributed to HR managers and senior leaders in Saudi NPOs. The survey included validated Likert-scale measures for behavioral selection practices, functional assessments, hiring pressure, government support, and organizational performance. Sample size consisted of 210 respondents from registered Saudi NPOs. Reliability was tested using Cronbach's alpha, and construct validity was assessed via confirmatory factor analysis (CFA). Multiple regression analysis and moderation analysis were conducted using SPSS.

4. DISCUSSION:

4.1. H1: Behavioural selection assessments has positive influence on the NPO performance.

As a Human resources practitioner, participated in more than 500 employees (white collar) at least 150 of them were senior levels. The NPOs once hire a senior leader depending on his behavioral assessment, they are most likely can predict his performance in the future and on the job, so he performs near what they expected from him and consequently the return on investment in such hiring is positive and the leader contributed in the NPO success. Specifically, most of the NPOs in Saudi Arabia are not specializing on industrial or sophisticated files so the success of the NPO depends in high percentage on the human resources mental and attitude in the same importance of their functional know-how or technical knowledge. To establish behavior selection assessment, it needs first to define it. It means depending on the candidate's experience or behavior towards some stated situations. Behavioral assessment depends on its baseline on the competencies needed to perform the job role.

Previously How the candidate is going to perform the job was early represented in **skills** needed to perform a position and many related studies tackled the skills of each position or task as the main enabler, then psychologists and HR practitioners developed the skills bank or skill inventory which is scanning all the organization employees skills and develop a unified inventory per person, on the other hand develop another theoretical one imagining what skills needed by each position then the matching process begins!. Ater the skills inventory it came the knowledge era, and practitioners started to argue that skills only are not sufficient to judge the employee performance and he needs to acquire specific knowledge to enable him to perform certain tasks. As an example, the sales need skill to communicate with clients but also need some knowledge to know the types of messages, types of clients and handling techniques. In this phase the answer to the question of HOW the candidate is going to perform in the position was: Knowledge + Skills.

Competency is defined as the combination of skills, knowledge, and attributes needed to perform a specific task or mission (Ivan T. Robertson, 2001) this combination solves the problem of the skills and knowledge exclusivity in job behaviors influence. As skills and knowledge are acquired things knowledge can be taught or learned and skill can be practiced, but they are not enough in driving someone's performance! There is something not acquired by aging but born with the candidate or at least grown with him in the very early age, this is the attribute, the attribute is the traits or self-conviction or in other words self-position from all human being, objects and situations faced by the person. For example like the offensive approach against street vendors it is not coming from any of skill or knowledge but it should

came from an offensive situation happened by his or her father or mother towards a street vendor and watched by the person in an early age or bad situation happened for some of his relatives from one of the street vendors, this perception grew with him and influenced his action towards the same type of sales persons, this describes the attribute, it's perception formulated in an early age. Also, a good example of the attribute when a father is depending on his young son or daughter in his/her early age in some logistical or admin issue at home or in the backyard, then it developed an accountable person that always be at his promises or gives a support in his persistence attribute.

The whole combination of the attribute with skill and knowledge develops the term competency. And to highlight the difference between skill and competency as we mentions regarding communication skill it is regarding how he is going to use his skill in sending and receiving messages, while the skill competency it is depending on (1) knowledge regarding types of messages, types or receivers communication definition and differentiating it from negotiation or influence speeches, (2) skill is the intrinsic usage of this knowledge in the daily situations and his acceptance from his listeners, (3) when we add the attribute to the same communication, it makes a wise usage like customizing the message upon the audience so as to assure their understanding, and send the appropriate message to the appropriate receivers using the appropriate Toole. This customization comes from the attribute and the whole mix produces the competency.

This bundle of three different components is not a tangible one, so when there is a need to develop any competency, we must return it to its three original components and see what component of them need certain development. I our last example if there is lack of communication competency and after analyzing the deficiency, we found that the practicing is the solution, so it is a skill gap, and we must sharpen the skill then return the bundle as it is. It's always important to look to the communication as a competency not as any of its components so as to have a holistic view of its acquired in the practical life and acquired in the early childhood -before the practical life- component although it is almost not a genetic one (Maas, 2012).

Assessment of the competency: To reach a fair assessment of competency towards an applicant for a position we should first keep away from its title, and at the same time keep its connected components. Here comes the role of descriptive behaviors. Judging a candidate on his problem-solving competency without knowing what it means in a descriptive behavior considered a major kind of bias, as the interviewer is judging him upon his own understanding of the problem solving which is different from another interviewer's perception towards the same competency. I made an experiment inside my corporate, split my recruitment team into two groups and asked them to describe teamwork competency into three present simple behaviors and the results was as follows:

First team: describe the candidate that has good rate in teamwork competency:

- Sharing knowledge
- Communicates effectively.
- Solving team entire problems

Second team described the candidate that has good rate in teamwork competency:

- Communicates effectively.
- Update information timely
- Distribute tasks proactively.

The similarity between the two groups was 33% while the deviation was 66%, I repeated this experiment on my HR delivered programs for 20 different organizations and the result was deviation between 66% and 100%! These results assure our major discrepancies in perception towards one single competency and obligate us to unify its behaviors describing that competency and its main description. In a UK organization they asked me to deliver 50 coaching sessions for their corporate enterprise sales managers on 6 already rated competencies. When I asked them to give me the competency description, I found the competency under the title negotiation has behaviors describing problem solving! And after I communicated with the HR team clarifying the issue as I thought it may be printing mistake, they assured that there is no mistake they described the negotiation competency internally as a part of solving their client problem and they must solve their client problem through negotiation. For a while I was astonished then when I revised what we are always describing that competency should be unified in its description across the organization not the whole world, I discovered that it is there right to describe it their own description and share it with their employees and leaders in order to know how they are evaluated and create a common language regarding each and every competency.

Competencies' selection: After describing each competency into certain behaviors we start the preparation phase which is not directly related to the interviews or assessments but acts as the main foundation for it. In the preparation phase we have now set of competencies important to the NPO different occupation. We start formulating mixed HR and functional teams in one committee representing the organization and have sufficient knowledge regarding most of the positions. If this team doesn't have that clear understanding, we may nominate one functional guy at each workshop talking the same functional titles. Design set of work shops to study two main aspects. First studying each competency and its correlation with the field of the NPO and its whole positions, in this phase they are mixing some behaviors, connecting or merging others, even they may merge two competencies in order to reach there common language and implicit perception towards these set of competencies, and the end of this phase they are reviewing all behaviors under each competency and approving it to be the main descriptor for that competency that will be frozen for a few years. The result of this phase called competency dictionary. There is an optional phase related to the size of the NPO, if it has more than 3 reporting levels the committee will work on differentiating each competency into two or three levels of proficiency. This may be hard to them to work on separately so there should be a competency advisor in the group or dealing with an external party to facilitate this phase with them. The result will be a set of competencies. Each competency has three levels elementary – mid level – and professional level, each level has set of behaviors describes the specific level. This activity shouldn't take place unless the NPO is a big size with more than three management levels or is going to expand or merge with another NPO.

Competency types: this is the second phase of workshops facilitated by the NPO competency advisor. In this phase the committee firstly classifies the competencies into three main domains acting as the major competency types. (1) Core competencies: these are the competencies shared between all NPO positions, no position is away from using these set of competencies and they are using them in very high frequency. All the organizational levels applied for any title will have these competencies in their job descriptions after hiring, job evaluation, and performance assessment sheets. (2) the leadership competencies: these competencies are not shared between the whole NPO titles, they are assigned only for supervisory levels and used in the assessment of the leader position only with its different

levels, examples are decision making, leading, and supervising, strategic planning. (3) Functional competencies, these are competencies that enable certain position to perform their technical or functional roles, they are tending to be specialized competencies and the committee put these competencies after deep analysis for the whole organization positions and job descriptions and after having very high frequency usage while discussing the competency titles in the dictionary. Functional competencies like analysis, innovation, and creativity.

We must note here that functional competencies in one organization may be core competencies on another organizations like innovation as functional competency in NPO working in the childcare, it may be a core competency for an NPO working on creative solutions to decrease poverty types. Specifying whether the competency is core or functional is the major and minor importance of the competencies shared between the whole positions and the critical common competencies in most positions.

Competency behaviors and occupations in this activity the committee is discussing and revising the whole NPO positions and job description to assign set of competencies with its related behaviors to each position. Job description is set of responsibilities should be carried by the job holder order to achieve the main target of the position, so if we have a small NPO consists of five persons so the main mission of the NPO is achieved by combining five job descriptions together without any gray areas not assigned to someone. Assigning competencies for positions may not be easy for the first workshops as once any member is revising the competency printed cards, he feels a tendency to assign the whole competencies for each position. Each position holder uses many competencies to perform a certain mission, but they should focus on the main competencies needed to perform their main responsibilities in their job description. That will lead them to decrease the competencies for each position.

Number of competencies needed for each position: typically, the market practice is assigning 6 to 8 competencies for senior levels 4 to 6 Competencies for supervisory levels, 1 to 5 competencies for the specialist levels with all its minor levels regarding the Competencies. After assigning some competencies for each position, it should be classified to Functional Competencies Core Competencies and senior leadership competencies if the position is a managerial or supervisory one. After assigning for each position, it's classified competencies even it is functional or core competencies we reached a final product called **competency map** or competency wheel. This competency map acting as the main matrix in selecting each position or assessment for each position each time we're going to assess any applicant at certain position we should have the job description plus the competencies assigned specifically to this position. These two main documents should be prepared before any interview if we are going to behaviorally assess this applicant.

Types of behavior assessments: depending on the behaviors to assess any leadership position we have a variety of tools and techniques, and we are going here to illustrate the most famous tools from them, taking into considerations that each tool has its importance and performance prediction percentages in many studies related to occupational psychology.

Competency based interview (CBI) the main and most famous technique, it depends on the past behaviors of the candidate, and how he reacted on certain situations revealed after the interviewer is tackling certain competencies through past situations, all the interview questions come in the post and asking the candidate to tell how he reacted in the past at a real situation not a situational or hypothetical situations. While the candidate is telling the story or how he reacted towards a certain situation, the interviewer is assessing the candidate on his

behavior. The CBI is depending on the wisdom “the past is the best predictor for the future” so when the interviewer asking a question as an example, tell me a situation that you had to close an important deal with an important strategic client. This question aims to assess the negotiation competency in the applicant interviewee. When the interviewee is answering this question, he has to tell a story or situation happened actually in the past with him, and while he’s answering the question or telling the story he is giving the interviewer a very good material to judge this competency on this interviewee, and can come up with a good prediction percentage on the same competency, how he is going to act in that certain situations or similar situations in the future if he took the hiring decision towards this candidate, moving from Question to another and building all the questions on the past tense to reveal the candidates actions done by him in the past and when reaching to the end of the interviewee, the interviewer will have complete picture regarding the competencies assigned for this position previously in the preparation phase, and can judge or predict his future performance if they are going to hire him in the NPO.

Assessment Centers: AC is one of the behavioral assessment activities, most likely used to assess leadership positions due to its time consuming and expensiveness. The assessment centre usually is conducted for set of leaders applying for the same position it consists of set of activities at least three activities. the activities arrange from the most frequently used to the least one is CBI, group discussion, role play and analysis presentation. These activities are supported by psychological assessment tool like emotional intelligence test or occupational personality questionnaire to reveal the comparison between the assessment centre activities results (the assessor’s point of view) and questionnaire results (the candidate self-awareness and his self-personality judgement).

In the group discussion, every candidate takes a different document has challenge and asking him to analyse this challenge. The group consists of at least three candidates up till six candidates. The combination of the six documents has multiple solutions for the problem, but each one has different role should be played to solve this problem. Each one has 20 to 30 minutes to read his document and prepare to play his role in solving this group problem. In the group discussion after each one read his document, the group discussion starts, and there are some assessors sitting behind the group, the assessors starting to make their assessment for the candidates while they are communicating with each other and trying to solve this problem. the distributed papers over them has some contradictions and they consequently has contradicting roles to be played and multiple interests that is not at the same direction for example one of them is playing the role of the financial manager who tries to decrease costing challenge and the other is a sales guy that is trying to give some discounts for clients and at the same time the third one has a merchandise problem and the goods are going to rise in cost, and he need to buy big portion of goods and put them in the stores which is contradicting with the financial managers objective. Assessors in this group discussion are assessing the same competencies being assessed while they were in the CBI to take complete judgment from different perspectives, but on the same competencies for each position after ending the activity the candidates are given few minutes break then enter the third activity which is role play.

Role play: it is an activity depending on the leader’s ability to handle conflict with his subordinate or manager in a full simulation situation, the leader is given a document illustrating a challenge or a problem faces his subordinate in this document he will find some situations, emails or complaints from clients or colleagues or other managers from his subordinate. Also, he will find some track performance records or achieved numbers, like sales targets’ actual achievement versus planned, the leader is given 20 to 30 minutes to digest all the document.

Then he starts to play the role of the manager of this country. The role of the assessor here is playing the subordinate role simulating the same problems faced him while he's playing this role as a subordinate of his manager he is assessing the leaders attempt to solve his challenges or problems, using the same competencies assigned for his actual position, the activity run over another 20 to 30 minutes after it ends, the assessor will have another judgment and evaluation perspective regarding the competencies of this leader.

Analysis presentation: In this activity, the candidate is given a full documentation of a case faces an organization mentioning all dimensions of this challenge like figures, income statements, balance sheets, emails, board meetings, strategic decisions, and previous plans. The role of the candidate is to read the full document in 90 minutes try to figure out the root cause of the problem analysing figures, plans and directions and come up with some solutions to completely solve the problem or partially decrease its negative impact lying on the organization mentioned in the case. after the 90 minutes presentation preparation he is going to present in 15 minutes to the assessor and he must tackle all the dimensions of the problem demonstrating complete digestion of the challenge and come up with some solutions, no matter is how the presentation looks like because the target of the assessor is assessing his same competencies while analysing this problem and trying to solve the challenge. Then the assessor has another 15 minutes to make some interventions some clarifications from the candidate to assure that he completely covered the challenges in the case. All the AC activities or the single CBI activity are made to stand on a complete evaluation for the candidate's behaviour and come up with future behavioral prediction and assure his fitting to the position nominated to fill.

Behavioural selection quality results: As a consulting NPO we received request to hire 12 leaders in multiple positions to 4 NPOs. We started with each NPO from the job description phase for each leader at each position then we move forward to develop a simple competency map for the selected positions and after developing suggested certain behaviours under each competency and take the approval from the top management we started to make the sourcing phase which end up with nominated candidates for each position, we started the exploration preliminary screening over the phone or online meetings, in order to assure that the received biographies or CVs are qualified enough to be nominated for the second screening phase, which is the CBI. After interviewing at least two or three candidates for each position from the 12 positions, we started to make the shortlist after the CBIs' report generated. For 10 positions we stopped at nominating two shortlisted candidates for the next functional interview phases and for the rest two position we received request to go for extra mile in the screening by designing an Assessment centre for each position. The two positions are CEOs for NPOs, and we started to prepare the cases and organize one complete assessment day for six shortlisted candidates targeting to choose two CEOs from that group.

The assessment day started with the group discussion, then role plays interchangeably with analysis presentations, there was three assessors working parallel in this AC and two organizers to organize the timetable activities for each of the six candidates. By end of day, we started for three days to conclude the assessment reports, the distribution of assessors over the candidates aimed to let the candidates pass by each assessor in one activity and being assessed on the same competencies but in different activities. Reports generated and concluded on one page evaluation matrix comparing the six candidates over the same competencies with different rates. Presented the report to the top management and they took the decision to hire the highest rates and start offering them.

To assure of the quality of the AS output we followed their performance for the first three months and assured their passing for the probation period which means that the performance prediction regarding their competencies meets the management and stakeholder expectations, which for sure reflected on the NPO performance. One of the CEOs developed the NPO new strategy and implemented over the past year complete organizational transformation. This is the ultimate positive impact of behaviourally selecting the leaders of NPOs.

4.2. H2: The Functional selection assessment has a positive influence on the NPO performance.

There are three major practices in the employee selection, behavior assessment and selection, functional assessments and selections, and direct nomination and hiring without passing any type of assessment before hiring. In this part I will illustrate the importance of functional assessment. Without functional assessment it is not related to the NPO success, it may lead if made wrongly to the NPO failure. Suppose that the NPO is hiring a costing accountant without testing his costing know-how or accounting capabilities. Then after hiring and while he is working silently, they discovered after few months that he made wrong costing attempts that lead to wrong estimation of the funds should cover these costs. That may lead to NPO non-achievement for a complete year targets and shortage in its community services that year, or it may lead in some cases to NPO shutdown. So, on the other side when hiring a well-tested and assessed costing employee how could reach a professional analysis of all the NPO direct and indirect costs and lead them to good financial planning and resources program, that will lead to an NPO success.

FSA Preparation phase: While the functional assessment has no behavioral aspects, so the base of the assessment is the functionality and technical specialization of each position so the preparation phase for the FSA depends on the responsibilities and key accountability for the position which should be written obviously in the job description, the functional interview depends on assuring that each and every responsibility written in the job description can be carried successfully by the candidate, also reviewing the CV of the candidate and assuring that the technical abilities written are real, and in the beneficiary of the NPO. Typically, the FSA comes after the BSA not before, to benefit from the shortlisted candidates and be sure that the nominated candidates must major problems with the position competencies.

If the process flipped and started with the FSA it may not benefit the relationships between the HR and technical line managers as if they interviewed candidate technically and then this candidate is rejected competency wise it needs very high consideration from the line manager to understand the bad consequences of hiring a guy with competencies deficiencies. This consideration is not always there as they are more towards task orientation and much away from the personality and competencies areas. For these reasons we always recommend that the HR conduct their CBIs and then nominate the shortlist to the line managers, then the line managers choose whoever from the short listed as it is exclusively their final decision. One of the organizations once depended exclusively on the functional interviews and chose industrial manager to work on its newly opened branch, they selected him due to his wide industrial experience and high functional industrial knowledge without any behavioral testing. After few months of this hiring the head office discovered that this leader started to cut the factory cost with unethical practices like preventing the laborers from wearing their safety tools, critical injuries happened, and a firefighting employee had serious burns in his body due to some cut cost decision this leader took. This indeed clarified to the board the mistake they did by hiring a leader depending only on his technical know-how, and although this leader achieved all the industrial targets, but the board lost the morale of the whole workers and began on the mid-

term express strikes and work stoppages due to the unsatisfied workers, which lead to more loss exceeded the short-term industrial achievements by the leader. Here we conclude that it is very important to assess the leaders functionally but not depending on this type of assessment exclusively and ignore the BSA.

4.3. H3: The pressure to hire has negative influence on the NPO performance:

When the NPO has pressure to hire it seems that they are in a good situation as they are expanding rapidly, but it is totally misleading perception. When some financial resources are injected in the NPO through an entity or even donor at most cases the entity or donor is directing the NPO to direct this fund in specific program, here came the pressure to hire more resources within a short period of time in order to fulfil the gained program which most probably it has one fiscal year fund so they start compromising the hiring conditions and consequently they got wrong persons in some places, which taking the NPO performance down even behaviorally or functional (Joseph Amankwah-Amoah, 2015). While leading the NPO recruitment team and trying to deal with the continuous expansion of the organization, we started to develop a service level agreement with all departments of the NPO in order to stand on an agreed on targets and time to fill each position, and each level on a pre-defined matrix communicated to them formally and documented in SLA, the most important part in the SLA is TTF or time to fill each position. This acted as the guardian from the pressure enemy, so as not to put an accelerated pressure or obligate the recruitment team to bypass some conditions or some quality standards to fill the accelerated needs and gaps.

One of the best practices to deal with the expansion pressure to hire is to utilize the low season hiring requests and prepare a talent pool of candidates by sourcing and exploring them, it takes few minutes to explore the candidate and communicate to him that we are preparing a legitimate talent pool for coming hiring phase. It needs an organized personnel planning and forecasting for the NPO expected needs from multiple resources, calibrating the resourcing channels to work on the most effective and efficient recruitment channels to get the maximum benefits from it. Channels may include referrals who are employees nominated from other current employees, it is one of the best sourcing channels as the employee recommending the candidate knows the current culture and organization environment very well and the nominated candidate by him most likely to be retained that the external sources of candidates. Also, there is a perception shared in a big portion of the community beneficiaries that NPOs are hiring leaders who have no places in the private sector because of their low qualifications. Although it is a wrong perception, but what is deepening this perception is the pressure to hire and compromising the behavioral and technical qualifications to hire rapidly in order to satisfy the NPO needs, and the accelerated NPS human resources requirements, so the pressure to hire and rush to hire calibres bypassing testing their qualifications thoroughly has other indirect negative impact on the community perception towards the NPS leaders, beside the direct negative impact on the performance of the NPO itself.

4.4. H4: Government financial support has a direct both positive and negative impact on NPOs performance:

on 2019 we signed a two-year contract with the developmental housing association to establish 30 developmental housing NGO and building the human resources capacity for another 30 existing housing development NGOs. One of the deal items was hiring three employees in the newly established NGOs and the already running ones. Before the deal signage the 30 existing NGOs was suffering from lack of funds an inability to hire the needed

candidates and they was depending on volunteers to run their community activities which is not reliable or sustainable. But immediately after the deal signed and we choose the NGOs, they rushed into hiring the candidates trying to bypass the hiring procedures to get the benefits of the 24-month funding! Because of this and many examples we faced while working with NPOs we reached the hypothesis that the governmental financial support is a double-edged weapon. To decrease its bad effects and increase its benefits, some conditions should be assigned with the same fund as some qualifications conditions in hiring, transparent process, performance evaluation reports should be submitted to assure the right guy working in the right places for the benefit of the NPO.

4.5. H5: Government non-for-profit sectors' regulations has a direct both positive and negative impact on NPOs performance:

According to Saudi Arabia 2030 vision (Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, 2016) the kingdom planned to raise the non-for profit sector contribution in the national GDP by more than 5% so the government started to facilitate the NPO establishment with more easier regulations in order to encourage the founders to establish NGOs and serving their community. Some of these regulations does not obligate the founder or the CEO of the NPO to be a full-time employee as a result of this the NPO for many daily hours operated by mid or junior levels without the existence of senior levels who are working in other private sector organizations and spending some of their spare time in the NPO also some of the regulations when it came easier towards establishment of the NPOs they accelerated specially from the year of 2015 to the year 2023 which double the number of the non-NPO's From 1500 to 3340 NGO (King Khalid Foundation, 2023). This accelerated establishments put high pressure on the human resources should be hired and work in the NPOs and may be diluted the impact of the interventions of the NPO in the same community area that also created some competition between the NGOs, working in the same area, and even in the same field, having all these regulations in mind, we can conclude that the government regulations has both positive and negative impact on the NGOs performance. To decrease the negative impact and increase the positive impact of these regulations, it needs further legalization and governance to be developed and spread over the NPOs to prevent potential competitions and deepening the community programs impact also, encouraging the founders and senior leaders to work as full-time employees in the NPOs.

5. CONCLUSION:

Using one BSA like, CBIs, or Activities from the AC for leaders like role plays or group discussions and supported by one type of behavioral self-answered questionnaires like emotional intelligence or personality assessment questionnaire is crucial for senior leaders' performance prediction, which has significant impact on NPO's overall performance. Depending on the functional assessments only will not lead to complete or accurate selection for the senior leader. It will lead to choose a good leaders knowing the technical aspects of the job, knowing the functionalities of his position but will not predict how he will mix all these knowledge or even experience in the new nominated job role, what are the behaviors should be demonstrated while facing challenges, or solving problems, what are the proofed competencies to enable him to succeed in his new role, all these needs and predictions will not be able to be done unless the employee is behaviorally assessed.

Assessing leaders' behaviours before hiring recommends baseline formulation, like assigning certain competencies and behaviours for each position, and because of this prepared baseline,

there are huge benefit, even after hiring this leader as now, the NPO has standardized behaviours the leader will be accessed periodically upon these behaviours and enable them to clearly decide the leader's probation period passing successfully. Also, after the periodical performance period there will be development and training need to support this leader also depending on these standard behavior's evaluation, the NPO can benefit from this also, in building career paths, succession planning for leaders, pay-for-performance, and competency-based compensation schemes. Therefore, the behaviorally assessed and selected leaders, including its preparatory phase has great benefit for the performance and success of the NPO. Human capital management come at the heart of the NPO, and serving the community come in the heart of the NPO mission, vision, and values, so NPO is depending on people to serve other people in a complete humanitarian servicing valued circle which lead to the crucial importance of the careful selection for the NPO human capital and as the community services depending a lot on the behaviors demonstrated while achieving the community programs and services so the behavioral selection playing vital role in the NPO performance and success.

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